

Grazing Under Photovoltaic Panels

The Utilisation of pastures under photovoltaic panels

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Shade in the pastures under photovoltaic panels, Agrogestiona farm, Granada

The Agrogestiona farm bases its agroforestry model on the use of several complementary resources, by means of sheep. Depending on the time of the year, these resources vary from a plot of almond trees, cereal stubble, Mediterranean scrubland, to the vegetation cover of this photovoltaic farm located in the Altiplano region of Granada. In this summary we will focus on the management of the photovoltaic plant, because this activity provides profitability and allows the recovery of the whole agroforestry system, at times of the year with lower pasture production.

The holistic pasture management on this farm achieves numerous benefits such as improved soil health, reduced erosion, increased biodiversity and organic matter, and a progressive increase in the number of annual species colonising the pasture. Achieving these objectives in this system, where tillage is conditioned by obtaining photovoltaic energy, is a challenge in which the role of the sheep is fundamental.

The animals benefit from the shade provided by the panels during their stay, in a region with one of the highest levels of sunshine in the Iberian Peninsula, with an average annual rainfall of less than 300 mm. The humidity that is generated under the panels, from the frequent fogs that cover the area of Granada Altiplano, is an invaluable asset that allows grass to grow where water condenses. The photovoltaic panels act as a condensation surface, which, together with the shading, allows grass to grow almost all year round on the strips of land covered by the structures.

In this way, not only does the flock benefit from the grass growing under the panels, but the energy company also benefits from the control of the grass by the sheep, because holistic pasture management ensures that the ground is covered with vegetation for a large part of the year. This is of great importance from the point of view of the efficiency of the solar panels, as the bare ground in such an arid region leads to a large amount of dust being deposited on the panels and entails high labour and water costs for cleaning.

The use of grazing under the panels avoids the costs of herbicides or mechanical weeding that would be necessary for the proper maintenance of the roof and the operation of the panels.

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